

EUCLIDEAN SPACES OF 2, 3, 4, ..., n, DIMENSIONS

The procedure of representing (in a plane) the points defined in Euclidean spaces of one and two dimensions, has been considered solved for a very long time.

A two-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2$ can be represented in a plane so that the very plane of the projection is defined by the coordinate axes q_1 and q_2 . Thus in the projection plane $q_1 \perp q_2$.

A point $A_1 (Q_1, Q_2)$ defined in the system $q_1 \perp q_2$ is represented by drawing a parallel from point Q_1 on the axis q_1 , with the axis q_2 , and a parallel with axis q_1 from point Q_2 on the axis q_2 . The intersection of these two lines determines the projection (in a plane) of point $A_1 (Q_1, Q_2)$, defined in a two-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2$ (image 1)*.

However, the problem of representing a three-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3$ in a plane is somewhat more complex. One of the basic traits of the two-dimensional E -space allows for the possibility of no more than two lines to intersect at a right angle. Which means that it is not possible to represent a three-dimensional E . space in a plane so that $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3$. As a solution to this problem the following procedure has been adopted: if the plane of the projection is determined by axes q_1 and q_2 then in that case in the plane of the projection $q_1 \perp q_2$. The third axis q_3 is represented so that it does not form right angles with q_1 and q_2 in point 0 with the condition that in the three-dimensional E . space which is represented $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3$. This means that in this procedure it is assumed that the q_3 axis is perpendicular to q_1 and q_2 since this cannot be claimed for the two-dimensional E . space (image 2a).

One way to represent point $A_2 (Q_1, Q_2, Q_3)$ in this case is to first locate $A_1 (Q_1, Q_2)$ on the plane $q_1 \perp q_2$ and draw a parallel from Q_3 with OA_1 , and then from point A_1 a parallel with q_3 . The intersection of these two lines determines the projection of point $A_2 (Q_1, Q_2, Q_3)$ on the plane of the projection, defined by the axes $q_1 \perp q_2$ (image 2b).

If we now suppose the possibility of a four-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3 \perp q_4$, there is the problem of its representation in a plane (in Euclidean two-dimensional space). The solution is possible by applying an already explained procedure for the three-dimensional case. If we start with the three-dimensional system ($q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3$) represented in the plane $q_1 \perp q_2$, then the four-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3 \perp q_4$ can be represented on the plane $q_1 \perp q_2$, by drawing an axes q_4 from point 0, which (in the projection) in the general case does not need to be perpendicular to any of the projections of the other axes (the same goes for the q_3 axis, in this case) (image 3a).

This means that a system represented this way is a projection of a four-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3 \perp q_4$ on the plane $q_1 \perp q_2$. It is justifiable to assume such a projection plane in which none of the axes' projections $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3 \perp q_4$ would be perpendicular on the projection plane to the other three axes (image 3b).

Let's say that point $A_3(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4)$ is defined in a four-dimensional E . space and let's say that the projection of this system in a plane is given like in image 3a, then the procedure of determining A_3 in such a represented system is as follows: on the axes q_1, q_2, q_3 and q_4 we place the values of the coordinates of point $A_3(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4)$. From point Q_1 we draw a parallel with the axis q_2 and from Q_2 we draw a parallel with axis q_1 . The intersection of these two lines determines the projection of point A_1 on the plane $q_1 \perp q_2$. Then from Q_3 we draw a parallel with OA_1 , and from A_1 a parallel with q_3 . The intersection of these two lines determines the projection of point A_3 on the plane $q_1 \perp q_2$. If we now draw a parallel with OA_2 from point Q_4 and from point A_2 a parallel with the axis q_4 , then the intersection of these two lines represents the projection of point $A_3(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4)$ on the plane $q_1 \perp q_2$ (image 3c).

In the case of the four-dimensional E . space shown in image 3b, the procedure of determining point $A_3(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4)$ within it is shown in image 3d. It can be seen that the position of the projection of point A_3 on the plane does not depend on the order of operations that determine it. Based on everything written here, the problem of representing in a plane (a two-dimensional E . space) some n -dimensional E . space ($n \in N$) would be solved by representing projections of all axes through a point O in a plane with arbitrary mutual angles, while in the n -dimensional E . space it would be $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3 \perp q_4 \perp \dots \perp q_n$. So the projection of a six-dimensional E . space is $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3 \perp q_4 \perp q_5 \perp q_6$ on an arbitrary plane and the projection of some point $A_5(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4, Q_5, Q_6)$ defined in that space, is shown in image 4.

The analysis of thus defined multidimensional spaces leads to some more general conclusions. The axes of a two-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2$ determine a plane. The axes of a three-dimensional E . space $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3$ determine three planes: (q_1, q_2) ; (q_1, q_3) ; (q_2, q_3) , while the axes of a four-dimensional E . space determine six planes: $(q_1 \perp q_2)$; $(q_1 \perp q_3)$; $(q_1 \perp q_4)$; $(q_2 \perp q_3)$; $(q_2 \perp q_4)$; $(q_3 \perp q_4)$. This means that the axes of an n -dimensional E . space would determine the planes whose number is given by the sum:

So, it is possible to draw only two mutually perpendicular planes** through one line in a three-dimensional E . space. In a four-dimensional E . space it is possible to draw a maximum of three mutually perpendicular planes through one line (image 5).

In a five-dimensional E . space it is possible to draw a maximum of four mutually perpendicular planes through one line (image 6). Based on all this we can conclude that in the n -dimensional E . space it is possible to draw an $n-1$ number of mutually perpendicular planes.

*For easier deliberation in all the examples only positive aspects of the coordinate axes, since it is assumed that it does not greatly affect the heart of the problem.

** Two planes that have three or more common points (which do not belong to one line) are considered to be identical (we cannot distinguish them).

*** For simpler writing, $q_1 \perp q_2 \perp q_3$ is used instead of $q_1 \perp q_2, q_1 \perp q_3, q_2 \perp q_3$